

Beyond the Checklist: Are Gaelic Games' Concussion Protocols Supporting Psychological Recovery

Contact:

Dr Ed Daly,
Department of Sport, Exercise
& Nutrition, Atlantic
Technological University (ATU),
Dublin Road, Galway
Email: ed.daly@atu.ie

Further Reading:

Daly, E. & Ryan, L. (2025) A
qualitative analysis of existing
concussion return to play
protocols and psychological
recovery management in Gaelic
Games. *International Journal of
Sports Science and Coaching*, 20,
225 – 235.
DOI: 10.1177/17479541241289983

Daly, E., Ryan, L. (2024). Athlete
perspectives on concussion
recognition and management in
Gaelic games: A qualitative
analysis. *Healthcare*, 12(19), 1974.
DOI: 10.3390/healthcare12191974

National Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) Theme:

Life Sciences, Medtech & Medical
Devices

Acknowledgement:

The author wishes to sincerely
thank their co-author, Dr Lisa
Ryan, Head of School of Health,
Sport Science & Nutrition at ATU.

*The content and views included in this
policy brief are based on independent,
peer-reviewed research and do not
necessarily reflect the position of
RISE@ATU.*

RISE@ATU is co-funded by the Government
of Ireland and the European Union through
the ERDF Northern & Western Regional
Programme 2021-2027.

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Concussion (or mild traumatic brain injury) is a frequent but often poorly managed injury in Gaelic games. Current return-to-play approaches focus mainly on physical symptoms, while psychological recovery such as anxiety, fear of re-injury, and social isolation are rarely addressed. Inconsistent and poorly enforced protocols combined with uneven concussion education across clubs and counties further increase risks to player welfare. The objectives of this research are to highlight gaps in current concussion management, emphasise the importance of psychological recovery, and support the development of consistent, enforceable, and player-centred concussion policies across all levels of Gaelic games.

Research Findings

Qualitative data from Gaelic games athletes indicates that concussion recovery is often poorly structured and inconsistently applied. Psychological effects such as anxiety, low mood, fear of re-injury, and loss of sporting identity were commonly reported, yet rarely addressed in formal recovery processes. Athletes described pressure to return to play, limited access to specialist support, and confusion around recovery timelines. Concussion education was variable, and many players only recognised the seriousness of concussion after experiencing it themselves. Overall, current practices prioritise physical clearance while neglecting mental and emotional recovery.

Policy Implications

Polymakers should recognise concussion (or mild traumatic brain injury) as a whole-person injury requiring both physical and psychological management. There is a clear need for visible, enforceable return to play protocols which apply consistently across all Gaelic sports and playing levels. Psychological screening and support should be embedded within concussion pathways. Regular and mandatory education for coaches, referees, medical staff, and players is required to improve recognition, reduce stigma, and prevent premature return to play. Clear governance and accountability mechanisms are essential to ensure protocols are followed in practice, not just in policy.

Industry Recommendations

The Gaelic Games Association (GAA) should promote a single, standardised concussion return to play framework which includes psychological recovery checkpoints. Sideline decision-making should be supported by objective assessment tools, reducing pressure on players to self-report or minimise the injury. Teams (club and intercounty) should be supported with access to trained personnel and clear referral pathways for psychological support. Regular education programmes should be delivered across all levels of Gaelic games. These measures would enhance player welfare, reduce long-term health risks, and strengthen confidence in concussion management systems in the GAA.

